

Sample ID **1-3 (Combined)**

Operator ID **user**

Notes

Elapsed Time	00:01:00
Median Diam.	86.7 nm
Mean Diam.	102.5 nm
Polydispersity	0.395
GSD	1.781

Lognormal Size Distribution

d(nm)	G(d)	C(d)	d(nm)	G(d)	C(d)	d(nm)	G(d)	C(d)
33.6	26	5	75.0	97	40	128.0	80	75
41.4	44	10	80.7	99	45	141.0	70	80
47.7	58	15	86.7	100	50	157.7	58	85
53.4	70	20	93.3	99	55	181.8	44	90
58.8	80	25	100.4	97	60	224.1	26	95
64.1	87	30	108.3	93	65			
69.5	93	35	117.4	87	70			